

Software Services and Data Analytics for the ultimate EV Driver experience

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Abstract

The gradually increasing momentum behind electromobility adoption – both from the side of the consumer and the automotive industry – suggests that electromobility will play an important role in Europe’s mobility going forward. According to (Engel, Hensley, Knupfer, & Sahdey, 2018), more than 350 new Electric Vehicle (EV) models are expected by 2025, with ranges that increasingly top 200 miles. However, not having enough access to efficient charging stations (McKinsey, 2017) is the third most serious barrier, behind high prices and low driving range, and brings uncertainty surrounding the attitude and purchasing behaviour of consumers in the market place. To tackle this issue, NeMo has developed a set of end-user services and a platform called Hyper-Network aiming to improve end-users electromobility experience and access to end-users electromobility related services.

Keywords:

ELECTROMOBILITY, END-USER SERVICES

1. Introduction

Electromobility is a major factor towards transport decarbonisation. However, a number of challenges limit the potential for interoperable and seamless electromobility services to a wider range of actors and geographic areas, hindering electromobility adoption.

Some of these barriers are technological limitations such as limited electric vehicles driving range or other infrastructural limitations such as low availability of public charging infrastructure (Wolinetz & Axsen, 2017) and lack of interoperability between cities and countries. All of them bring uncertainty surrounding the attitude and purchasing behaviour of consumers in the market place.

The NeMo project (“Hyper-Network for electro-**M**obility”) is working to improve the electromobility experience by developing a set of end-user services and a platform called Hyper-Network to provide seamless interoperability of electromobility services. Some of these services developed in NeMo, act as a basis for a simulation and modelling of EV users’ behaviour to subsequently model the charging points offer and demand. NeMo also deals with all the vehicle and personal data offering the EV owner to manage it, with strong focus on data privacy and security. This paper will focus on the importance of increasing EVs public acceptance by analysing mobility user patterns, trying to combine

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charging with users' everyday activities through these NeMo services.

2. The NeMo Project

NeMo has created a pan-European eRoaming Hyper-Network of tools and services that allows seamless and interoperable use of electromobility services throughout Europe. Also, NeMo provides an Open Cloud Marketplace, where third parties can provide services (B2B and B2C) aiming to increase EV attractiveness.

A main factor limiting EV driving range is lack of interoperability in existing charging infrastructure and related electromobility services. Electromobility actors currently have to deal with a broad spectrum of EV charging systems hardware, service providers, standards and protocols, which can vary greatly from a technological perspective. NeMo analyses the current regulatory frameworks relevant to electromobility, identifies barriers and proposes regulatory measures at national and European level. Additionally, it extracts interoperability and regulatory requirements for electromobility in general and specifically for the NeMo Hyper-Network.

All electromobility actors (including EV users) will have seamless access to all available ICT services in this interconnected data-hub/network. The same applications will apply to all charging providers and the user will be presented with an extended, homogenous and unified charging network. This seamless provision of ICT services will make EVs more user-friendly, thus boosting the electromobility adoption rates.

The Hyper-Network is a distributed environment with an open architecture based on standardised interfaces, in which all electromobility actors, physical (i.e. Charging Points - CPs, grids, EVs) or digital (i.e. Charge Point Operators - CPOs, Distribution System Operators - DSOs, etc.), can connect and interact seamlessly, exchange data and provide more elaborate electromobility ICT services. So, NeMo is not a proprietary platform for electromobility but a full open eco-system allowing continuous and uninterrupted provision of data and services.

The Open Cloud Marketplace (see Figure 1) can be considered as a space where players with similar interests can search for business partners and trade their goods: in this case e-mobility related IT services. In NeMo, different 'marketplace nodes' are deployed which allow each player to participate in the marketplace established by a breathing network of marketplace participants. All possible business models are studied, in order to achieve this information exchange in a commercially exploitable manner.

Figure 1: De-centralized Marketplace

In order to verify and validate the NeMo Hyper-Network and services, different tests have been carried out at sites in France, Germany, Spain, Austria and Italy. Each test site has specific characteristics and has unique needs in terms of electromobility, which make them complementary. Based on these specificities, test scenarios have been defined to demonstrate the benefits of the NeMo Hyper-Network in each one.

To validate NeMo’s true pan-European eRoaming capabilities a cross-country test will be performed, using electromobility services seamlessly and interoperable while travelling through Europe. This final cross-country test drive will take place starting and ending in Barcelona, via France, the Netherlands, Germany, Austria, Italy and France, coinciding with the 2019 ITS European Congress (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Cross-country test drive

3. EV Driver services

NeMo will facilitate increased service availability, better planning and more secure electric grid operation, by making backend data and services accessible to the right actors and bringing down digital (interfaces) and physical (location) barriers.

EV Driver services act as facilitating services of core components to other services and have different capabilities explained in Figure 3.

Figure 3: EV Driver services' capabilities

Service brokerage, CPO monitor and profiler and EV driver monitoring and profiling have been designed and developed as specific services integrated on top of the NeMo Hyper-Network, aiming to add intelligence to other electromobility services.

3.1 EV driver monitoring and profiling

This service collects data from EV drivers in order to profile them. The generated profile will contain users' charging preferences, driving preferences, recurrent places, recurrent trips and contact information. Table 1 shows different functionalities of this service.

Functionality	Description
Collect track data	Receive geolocation data from frontend applications that can access to the GPS sensors
Process track data	Abstract places and recurrent places from raw track data
Manage EV driver profile	Offer an interface which EV drivers can edit their profile
Expose EV driver profile	Let third party access EV driver profiles (with the explicit authorization of the driver)

Table 1 – EV driver monitoring and profiling functionalities

Figure 4 explains the input required for this service. EV driver profile, as the output, will set up the charging and driving preferences, recurrent places and trips and contact information for the Service Brokerage.

Figure 4: Input and Output Data (EV Driver monitoring and profiling)

3.2 CPO monitoring and profiling

This service monitors CPOs in order to profile them. To do so, a set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) offered by CPOs are consulted periodically. This data is processed to generate a profile for each CPO and make it accessible through the Hyper-Network. Generated profiles include: a list of charging pools, charging stations, charging points and charging connectors, with all the available information provided by the mentioned entities; Updated data of the availability status of the charging points, the frequency of the update depends on each CPO (in some cases, this information is updated in real time); and, Forecast availability of the charging points where forecasts are generated using machine learning techniques and the results are continuously updated to predict the status of each charging points at any time between the current moment and the following week. Table 2 shows different functionalities of this service:

Functionality	Description
Collect data from CPOs	Collect CPOs static and dynamic data such as CP availability, connector type, CP coordinates, ...
Machine learning models' generation	Using historic data
Produce forecasts	Using machine learning models
Generate profiles	Using collected data and availability forecasts
Offer profiles	Through the Hyper-Network

Table 2 – CPO monitoring and profiling functionalities

Figure 5 explains data input required for this service.

Figure 5: Input and Output Data (CPO monitoring and profiling)

3.3 Service Brokerage

The brokerage service aims to assist end users choosing the right charging station in terms of availability and price, while avoiding system congestions due to high demand of specific resources. The service brokerage takes the output generated in the CPO monitoring and profiling and combines it with the output from the EV driver monitoring and profiling to create a service that using the forecast of CP availability and the users’ preferences advises to the users the charging station that best fulfils their needs and provides a smart management of the grid.

Table 3 shows different functionalities of this service.

Functionality	Description
Point the best charging stations to be used for EV drivers that ask for it	The service is intended to receive requests asking for suggestions in the near future (1-2 hours), but it works up to one week in advance. The results are based on the time and place provided by the EV driver on the request and the availability forecast generated by the CPO Monitor.
Generate daily suggestions saying where EV drivers could charge their EV	Based on the EV driver recurrent places generated by EV Driver Monitor and the forecast availability generated by the CPO Monitor.

Table 3 – Service Brokerage functionalities

Figure 6 explains data input required for this service. Suggestions of CPs to be used, as the output, help EV drivers to decide where and when to charge their vehicles in order to balance the overall system load.

Figure 6: Input and Output Data (Service Brokerage)

Brokerage service has a lot of potential to be used in different front-end applications: either standalone applications or being used by existing applications to add functionality.

For instance, any CPO that has a frontend application could add the functionality provided by this service. By doing so, they could provide a better service to their users and at the same time, avoid congestions on the system.

4. OEM perspective: CRF prototype

A real demonstrator based on the electric vehicle Fiat 500e (2015 model year) has been developed by CRF for the Italian test site. The EV is equipped with an advanced Human Machine Interface (HMI) which allows the EV driver to plan all the aspects of a daily itinerary with the minimum effort thanks to the end-user services provided by the NeMo hyper-network. The high-level architecture below (Figure 7) shows in more details the main actors involved in the prototype. In particular, the HMI is connected in a secure way with the backend of the navigation provider installed on board which, in turn, is connected to the end-user services of NeMo.

Figure 7: CRF prototype architecture

The EV is also connected to the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) backend where all the vehicle and personal data are stored securely and can be managed by the EV owner. All the vehicle and personal data shared with the OEM backend, the navigation provider and the providers of the NeMo services are covered by specific contracts that, in accordance with EU data protection legislation, can be revoked at any time.

A typical electromobility scenario for the CRF prototype includes the following situations:

- i. **First itinerary planning.** The EV driver, at the beginning of the day asks the HMI to calculate the best itinerary to the usual destination on a weekday. The HMI by means of the Navigation Provider Backend (NPB) invokes firstly the Personal Mobility Probability (PMP) service in order to have the most probable path the user is going to take in a determined weekday and then, on the basis of the previous battery consumption profile invokes the *CPOBooking* service in order to have the availability of the charging points along the route.
- ii. **Charging point Booking.** If the EV driver confirms the proposed booking slots the *CPOBooking* is newly invoked.
- iii. **Battery monitoring.** During the trip, the battery status is continuously monitored by the NPB which verifies that the next charging point can be reached with a safe remaining charge. In case of higher consumption due to unplanned events like queues caused by incidents, the NPB sends to the HMI notifications with also an alternative route to a new and closer charging point. In case the EV driver accepts the advice, the *CPOBooking* is invoked again in order to 1) delete the previous booking and 2) book the new charging point.

5. Data Simulation and Visualisation

A simulation of the charging points system by studying the users' mobility and modelling the offer and demand is developed using the EV driver services developed in NeMo. It provides one of the potential applications of the service brokerage that puts together the perspective of regional authorities, stakeholders, customers and service providers. However, one of the issues of the service brokerage is that it needs a high volume of users to give intelligent suggestions, thereby a simulation of electromobility drivers has been executed.

To understand users' mobility patterns two approaches have been followed, a subjective approach coming from EV driver interviews and, an objective approach analysing the outputs of the EV driver and profiler. This service has been tested with a set of pilot users in the city of Barcelona, therefore recurrent places from the users and patterns have been extracted. Furthermore, surveys and a process of co-creation of the service have been carried out together with the user, to get significant insights of the service and to better model the user mobility patterns.

With data taken from surveys and from pilot users (using the EV monitoring & profiling), a clustering of users' profile has been performed and, afterwards, a simulation of EV drivers moving around the

city has been carried out. These simulation models take into account different travel behaviours such as electric taxi drivers, regular EV drivers, occasional users, etc.

The simulation and modelling are embedded in a Geographical Information System (GIS) framework with interactive maps and graphs to analyse the data dynamically and simulate the different electromobility scenarios.

6. Conclusions

This paper has described the importance of increasing EVs public acceptance by analysing mobility user patterns, trying to combine charging with users' everyday activities through these NeMo services. These technological solutions developed underlining the need of continuous and uninterrupted provision of data and services, bringing down digital (interfaces) and physical (location) barriers, aim to better plan and optimise charging infrastructure resources and to increase EV attractiveness.

Next steps related with data simulation and visualisation are planned in order to better optimise the selection of charging sites considering users' perspective, scalability issues and grid constraints. Moreover, a tool will be developed specially for public administrations and vehicle manufacturers (OEMs). It will implement a methodology to optimise the selection of charging sites considering users' needs and habits, time and costs, as well as scalability issues and grid constraints. It will help to understand how to plan and govern, by simulating the impact expected from electromobility strategies when the number of users in a city increases.

This tool will be fed by a model that integrates and analyses the city electromobility offer, the geographical topology and the population density and, it will compare them with the electromobility demand taken from EV drivers' behaviour simulation. In addition, it will use mathematical modelling and prediction to identify charging locations based on an approach that focuses on the load behaviour and urban mobility of users.

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